

WEAR BEHAVIOUR OF SILICON CARBIDE-FILLED GLASS/EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Glass fibre reinforced polymers traditionally show poor wear characteristics due to the very brittle nature of the reinforcement fibres. The present work is aimed at manufacturing a glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) composite material with improved wear and abrasion resistance. Starting from results produced by a previous study¹, optimisation has been achieved of some relevant material parameters in order to increase the frictional load bearing capabilities of the GFRP composite.

Laminates have been manufactured by hot-pressing stacks of glass fibre reinforced epoxy resin prepreg sheets. The surface matrix of both outer plies of the laminates has been filled with several different volume percentages of silicon carbide (SiC) powders. Powder embedment in the polymer matrix has been achieved by uniformly spreading pre-determined amounts of the filler onto the outer plies surfaces prior to hot-pressing consolidation and curing of the laminate. Two different grain sizes of the same powder have been individually tested: 600mesh and 2000mesh.

Wear tests have been carried out using a pin-on-disc apparatus, by placing the composite specimens in sliding contact with a steel disc. Test parameters such as sliding speed and contact pressure between the steel disc and the composite specimens have been varied, in order to determine the conditions yielding the best wear performance of the composites examined.

Key Terms: GFRP composites, Wear behaviour, SiC powders, Pin-on-disc

1. INTRODUCTION

An enhancement of wear resistance of composite materials would be a very interesting and highly desirable achievement in order to enlarge applicability of composites to new technology fields¹. Studies carried out by Cirino *et al.*^{2,3} on reinforced polymers sliding against steel evidenced the difference of the mechanisms involved in the wear of composite elements as well as the sequence by which such mechanisms occur throughout the wearing of the material. The first mechanism yielding the composite surface damage while sliding over a hard surface is the adhesive wear of the polymer matrix. This phenomenon consists of polymer particles removal from the composite surface; such particles are led to adhere to the hard surface upon the which the composite is sliding. In fact this causes the hard surface to be covered with a thin polymer layer and, as a result, the sliding action turns to be a polymer on polymer friction. There happen to be several points were microwelding between the polymer of the composite surface and that of the hard surface coating: such microwelding wears off further amounts of matrix from the composite surface. As soon as the matrix wear gets to a point where naked fibres are allowed to come in contact with the hard surface, new wear mechanisms occur, which prove extremely detrimental if the composite reinforcement is made of fibreglass. Glass fibres are hard enough to destroy the polymer coating previously deposited on the hard surface; furthermore, they are capable of producing a wear of the hard surface itself by abrasion. However,

glass fibres are very brittle, which causes them to easily break under the frictional load. Glass fibre fracture yields the presence of very hard and sharp debris between the surfaces sliding on each other, resulting in the establishment of the wear mechanism known as the three-body wear, which is extremely detrimental for both sliding bodies. In particular, such mechanism is capable to start a chain reaction, by which the composite material surface is quickly damaged after very effective matrix abrasion by the sharp and hard particles and new subsequent fibre breakage. Other studies^{4,5,6} took into consideration the influence of fibre length and orientation on the wear mechanisms sequence. However, little evidence exists of attempts to enhance the wear performance of composites.

This work is aimed at attempting an increase of GFRP composites by filling the polymer matrix with silicon carbide powders. Such hard powders were intended to protect the matrix from abrasion by the sharp glass particles coming from fibre breakage. Wear tests have been carried out following a pin-on-disc scheme to assess the wear resistance performance of the filled matrix: the sliding was established between composite specimens and a steel disc. Specimens have been manufactured containing several powder amounts. Different sliding pressure values have been adopted in separate test sessions, in order to highlight and explain the different wear mechanisms involved: this also allowed an understanding of the sliding conditions in which the highest friction performances of the composite material can be obtained.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. MATERIALS

GFRP composite laminates were manufactured using pre-preg sheets of epoxy resin filled with plain weave continuous fibre fabrics of 250gm^{-2} . Six pre-preg layers were stacked to fabricate the laminates; resin curing was achieved by hot-pressing the stacks at 120°C and under a 0.5MPa pressure for two hours. Both SiC powder filled laminates and powder-free laminates were made. Two grain size powders were separately utilised (600mesh and 2000mesh) and several laminates were manufactured with five different amounts of powder: 5%, 10%, 15%, 30% and 40% of powder with respect to the total matrix volume content. The powders have been embedded in the matrix by spreading them uniformly on both faces of the top lamina of the stack prior to curing: the spreading has been carried out by means of a manually operated mechanical sieve. This operation allowed the powders to be placed in the desired amount all over the surface of the specimens which was in sliding contact with the steel disc during the wear tests. All powder-free materials had a fibre volume as high as 58%, while fibre volume percentages between 55% and 56% were characteristic of the powder-added laminates. Pin-on-disc specimens were cut from the laminates having a square shape of 10mm linear dimensions: this resulted in an apparent contact surface area of 100mm^2 .

2.2. TEST METHODS

Wear tests were carried out using a pin-on-disc test apparatus equipped with a stainless steel disc, a frictional load cell and a vertical displacement sensor. Fibre orientation during the tests was in the radial and tangential directions with respect to the circular sliding trajectory on the steel disc. Track diameter was set to 230mm. Tests with two different values of the normal load were run: 30N and 50N, corresponding to applied pressure values of 0.3MPa and 0.5MPa . The linear sliding speed was 2.4ms^{-1} and all tests had a 60 minutes duration. At the end of each test the sliding track was polished by abrasive paper (size 2000).

Direct measurements of wear experienced by the materials have been obtained by monitoring the specimens' weight loss at the end of each 60min test. The material volume loss was calculated at a later stage.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All the tests showed an increase of the wear resistance of the SiC powder-filled materials with

respect to the powder-free laminates. Figures 1 and 2 show the weight losses recorded as a function of the powder volume content: the plots report data for both powder sizes used and for both applied pressure values adopted in the tests. The increase is shown of the wear resistance for all the materials: the weight loss is always less than in the case of powder-free material (powder percentage equals to zero). Moreover, it is clear that the beneficial effect of the presence of powders is more evident when a high contact pressure is applied. this equally applies to materials filled with powder of either sizes.

Figure 1. Weight loss for 600mesh-filled specimens.

Figure 2. Weight loss for 2000mesh-filled specimens.

Figures 3 and 4 report the trend shown by the specimens wear as a function of the powders amount: data refer to both powder mesh sizes and are plotted for both 0.3MPa and 0.5MPa contact pressures applied in the tests. These diagrams suggest the existence of an optimum value of the powders amount to be embedded in the composites, in order to achieve the best wear performance. The optimum value approaches 15% for the 600mesh powders, while it is close to 30% for 2000mesh powders. The explanation of this difference may be found in the consideration of a better packing efficiency achievable when finer powder grains are used: these can be better wetted and retained by the matrix, so resulting in a lower material loss, while the wearing develops.

Figure 3. Weight loss due to friction under 0.3MPa applied pressure.

Figure 4. Weight loss due to friction under 0.5MPa applied pressure.

Even more evident is the increase in wear resistance from the data relating to the volume loss, which are shown in Figure 5 and 6. The data shown were calculated by using the densities of the all the materials involved (the SiC density is of course sensitively higher than the resin density).

It clearly appears from Figures 5 and 6 that the wear resistance is increased by an increasing amount of powders up to a point where every new amount of powders embedded in the matrix proves detrimental. Above this amount the particles are hardly retained by the composite matrix during the sliding. As a result, particles can easily leave the resin matrix and become a third body in the friction. The effect of this on the wear is, however, very poor. Moreover, the free particles can also act as a little protection for the material from the sharp and hard debris coming from the glass fibre fracture when it starts.

Figure 5. Volume loss due to friction under 0.3MPa applied pressure.

Figure 6. Volume loss due to friction under 0.5MPa applied pressure.

In Figures 7 and 8 the friction coefficient trends are plotted for the different laminate types: values are comprised between 0.5 and 0.7 and a decrease is noticeable in correspondence with the powder amounts yielding the maximum increase in wear resistance. In Figure 9, the worn surface is pictured of a specimen filled with 30% amount of 600mesh powder. The presence of a considerable quantity of powder grains among the glass fibres is indicative of good powder dispersion and material meso-structure durability after severe frictional wear.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Pin-on-disc wear tests have proven the possibility to sensitively enhance the resistance of GFRP composites to frictional load when the polymer matrix is filled with hard silicon carbide powders. Tests have been carried out varying the applied normal load, the amount of powders in the matrix, the grain size of powders, so enabling a characterisation of the behaviour of the material under frictional

load conditions. Experiments evidenced that the presence of hard powders is capable of hindering the occurrence of adhesive wear phenomena, which typically affect the matrix; moreover, hard particles have a beneficial effect on the protection of the material from the damage caused by the sharp debris due to glass fibre breakage. The amount of powder to be embedded into the matrix in order to enhance the composite wear resistance has an optimum value, above which a further increase in the amount of hard particles in the polymer causes a faster wear of the material surface. This is thought to be due to a limit in the matrix capability to retain the ceramic particles during the sliding upon the hard steel surface; therefore, the hypothesis has been proposed that an amount of powders above the optimum gives birth to three-body wear mechanisms, which have the effect of damaging the composite to a larger extent than in the case of the optimum powder amount. The optimum value, in correspondence of which the maximum wear resistance is found, depends upon powders grain size and grain compaction within the matrix. Smaller grain powders (2000mesh) achieve a better compaction with respect to larger grains (600mesh). This also enables a higher content of powders to be possibly embedded in the polymer matrix in the case of smaller grains; therefore, in the latter case, a more effective wear protection of the composite becomes possible.

Figure 7. Friction coefficient values under an applied pressure of 0.3 MPa.

Figure 8. Friction coefficient values under an applied pressure of 0.5 MPa.

Optical microscopy observations showed that the matrix is capable of firmly retaining the powders embedded during laminate manufacturing. Powder grains continue to be finely distributed in the matrix and among the individual reinforcing fibres even after severe wear has developed, which caused extensive fibre breakage to occur.

Figure 9. Optical micrograph showing SiC particles onto the worn surface of a GFRP specimen (...×).

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